

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE NATURE OF ACTIVE COMPONENTS ON THE ACTIVITY OF REFORMING CATALYSTS

Babayeva F.A.,

Doctor of Chemical Science Associate Professor,

Y.H. Mamedaliyev's Institute of Petrochemical Processes, Azerbaijan

Abasov S.I.,

Doctor of Chemical Sciences, Professor,

Y.H. Mamedaliyev's Institute of Petrochemical Processes, Azerbaijan

Ahmadova R.H.,

Doctor of philosophy in chemistry,

Y.H. Mamedaliyev's Institute of Petrochemical Processes, Azerbaijan

Suleymanova T.I.

Doctor of philosophy in chemistry,

Y.H. Mamedaliyev's Institute of Petrochemical Processes, Azerbaijan

Abstract

A number of Pt-Re gasoline reforming catalysts have been synthesized, differing from each other in chemical composition and preparation method. The synthesized catalysts exhibit fairly high activity under the studied conditions ($T = 480-500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $V = 2.0\text{ h}^{-1}$, $P = 8\text{ atm}$ and $\text{H}_2/\text{feed} = 5.5$).

Keywords: catalytic reforming, activation, polymetallic oxide catalyst, aromatic hydrocarbons, gasoline fraction

Introduction Catalytic reforming is the most promising process for producing highly active gasoline and individual aromatic hydrocarbons.

The main direction for improving catalytic reforming is its intensification by increasing the depth and selectivity of aromatization of paraffin hydrocarbons contained in straight-run gasoline fractions. Increasing the depth and selectivity of aromatization of paraffin hydrocarbons can be achieved by using more efficient catalysts. Analysis of scientific and patent literature shows that reforming catalysts mainly contain Group VIII metals modified by additions of other elements [1-5].

Experimental method

For the process of reforming the gasoline fraction $85-180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, polymetallic oxide catalysts were synthesized, containing, in addition to platinum, rhenium, nickel, and cobalt, which significantly increase the stability of the catalyst. The objects of study were a number of synthesized oxide catalysts, which differed from each other both in the preparation method and in the chemical composition. The carrier was microspherical $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. The finished catalysts were thermostated at $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 hours, calcined at $350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 hours and $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 6 hours. The composition of the catalysts is given in table 1.

Table 1

Chemical composition of catalysts

Catalyst	Chemical composition of catalysts, % wt
KR-1	0.2 Re; 0.3 Pt / $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$
KR-2	0.2 Re; 0.3 Co, 0.3 Pt / $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$
KR-3	0.3 Re; 0.4 Ni, 1.0 La_2O_3 , 0.3 Pt / $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$
KR-4	0.3 Re; 0.3 Pt; 0.8 Co / $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$

The synthesized catalysts were tested in a flow-through installation under hydrogen pressure. 30 cm^3 of the catalyst under study was loaded into the reactor. Activation of the catalyst was carried out at $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a stream of air, then reduction with hydrogen was carried out at a temperature of $480\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The experiments were carried out under the following conditions: $T = 480-510\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $V = 1.5-2\text{ h}^{-1}$, $\text{H}_2/\text{raw material} = 5.6-6$, hydrogen consumption— 48 l/hour , $P_{\text{H}_2} = 8-12\text{ atm}$.

Testing of samples was carried out continuously for several hours with sampling every hour. The reaction products were analyzed on a chromatograph with a 50 m long capillary column filled with a liquid crystalline phase.

A fraction of straight-run gasoline $85-180\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was used as raw material.

Table 2

Composition of the initial gasoline fraction	
Indicators	Values
Density	0.7483
Refraction	1.4240
Compound %	
aromatics	6.6
naphthenes	27.7
paraffins	65.7

Results and Discussion

The studied catalysts exhibit fairly high dehydrogenating, isomerizing and dehydrocyclizing activity when reforming gasoline fractions at 85-180 °C. Thus, if the initial gasoline fraction contains 6.6 % of the mass of aromatic hydrocarbons, then after reforming its yield of aromatic hydrocarbons increases almost 10 times, the content of paraffin and naphthenic hydrocarbons decreases by 2 and 5 times, respectively. With increasing temperature of the experiment, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons on the KR-2 catalyst increases, while in the case of the KR-4 catalyst, which differs from KR-1 in chemical composition, it reaches a maximum at a temperature of 490 °C, and the activity of the catalyst is much higher. To increase the stability of Pt-Re catalysts are promoted with elements of groups IV-VIII. For this purpose, we conducted a study of the effect of the amount of cobalt on the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons during reforming of the gasoline fraction 85-180 °C. The introduction of 0.3 % Co into the composition of this catalyst leads to an increase in the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons at 500 °C by approximately 2 %. With a further increase in the cobalt content in the catalyst composition to 0.8 %, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons decreases and becomes less than in the case of the unpromoted KR-1 catalyst. At the same time, when comparing the dehydrogenating and dehydrocyclizing activities of the studied catalysts, it can be noted that Co-containing samples are characterized by greater

stability. For example, at 500 °C, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons in three hours of continuous operation decreases on the synthesized catalysts KR-1, KR-2 and KR-4 in the following sequence: by 4.5 %, 2 % and 1 %. When testing the KR-3 catalyst, it was found that the introduction of a platinum catalyst instead of 0.4 Ni and 1% La₂O₃ does not have a significant effect on the reforming ability of the catalyst.

In order to establish the reproducibility of synthesis conditions, KR-3(II) was synthesized and its tests in the process of reforming a gasoline fraction of 85-180 °C showed complete reproducibility. On Pt-Re catalysts during operation, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons decreases, i.e. the activity of these catalysts decreases. One of the reasons for the decrease in the activity of these catalysts is the sintering of Pt particles. There is information in the literature that sulfidation of Pt-Re catalysts with sulfur-containing substances slows down the sintering process of platinum and has a beneficial effect on the activity of the catalyst [1-5]. We prepared a catalyst sample sulfided with a mixture of 99.0 % H₂ + 1 % H₂S, which was tested in the process of reforming the gasoline fraction in a pilot plant under pressure. The obtained data are shown in table 3. As can be seen from the data presented, sulfidation of the KR-3(II) catalyst does not have a significant effect on its activity.

Table 3

The influence of sulfidation of the KR-3 catalyst on the reforming process of the gasoline fraction 85-180 °C. Experimental conditions: P = 8 atm, H₂ / feedstock = 5.5, V = 2.0 h⁻¹

Sample	Experiment temperature, °C	Catalyst composition, mass%		
		paraffins	naphthenes	aromatics
KR-3	480	60.24	5.76	33.65
	490	62.5	8.41	29.14
	500	6.29	8.68	28.03
KR-3 (II) sulfided	480	62.9	5.6	31.3
	490	64.7	7.6	27.7
	500	68.1	6.9	25.0

Thus, the study showed that the introduction of elements III and VIII gr into the Pt-Re catalyst has a significant effect on its activity in reforming the gasoline fraction 85-180 °C.

Conclusions. Synthesized catalysts for reforming gasoline, differing from each other in chemical composition and preparation method, exhibit fairly high activity under the studied conditions and are not inferior to the reference catalyst. Thus, on the KR-2 catalyst at a

temperature of 490 °C and V = 2.0 h⁻¹, the yield of aromatic hydrocarbons is 56 %.

The effect of different amounts of cobalt in the catalyst on its activity was studied. The introduction of 0.03 % Co has a beneficial effect on the activity of the catalyst by 5 %. In order to establish the reproducibility of synthesis conditions, KR-3(II) was synthesized and its tests during the reforming process showed complete reproducibility.

References

1. Di L., Xinyu L., Jinlong G. Catalytic Reforming of Oxygenates: State of the Art and Future Prospects / Chem. Rev. 2016, 116, 19, pp 11529–11653
2. Torbjørn G., Rune P., Anders H. Catalytic Reforming / Basic Principles in Applied Catalysis. 2004, pp 125–158
3. Le Tu A. Reforming of low-octane gasoline fraction on a mechanical mixture of catalysts N-TsVM and Pt, Re/ γ -Al₂O₃ / Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of technical sciences, Moscow, 2007
4. Maslyansky G.N., Shapiro R.N. Catalytic reforming of gasolines. L.: Chemistry, 1985.
5. Bely A.S. Current state, prospects for the development of the process and catalysts for reforming gasoline fractions of oil, 2014, pp. 23-28